

ISSN 2709-3409 (Online)

JOURNAL OF TERTIARY AND INDUSTRIAL SCIENCES

A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF THE HIGHER TECHNICAL TEACHERS'
TRAINING COLLEGE, KUMBA

**VOLUME 4, NUMBER 2
JULY, 2024**

**PUBLISHER:
HIGHER TECHNICAL TEACHERS' TRAINING COLLEGE (HTTC)
UNIVERSITY OF BUEA**

P.O Box: 249 Buea Road, Kumba
Tel: (+237) 33354691 – Fax: (+237) 33354692
Email: editor@jtis-httcubuea.com
Website: <https://www.jtis-httcubuea.com>

EDITORIAL BOARD

Supervision:

Professor Ngomo Horace Manga
University of Buea

Editor-in-Chief:

Prof. Akume Daniel Akume, University of Buea, Cameroon

Managing Editor:

Dr. Negou Ernest, University of Buea, Cameroon

Associate Editors:

Prof. Ebune B. Joseph, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Defang Henry, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Lissouck Daniel, University of Buea, Cameroon

Advisory Editors:

Prof. Tabi Johannes Atemnkeng, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Lyonga N. Agnes Ngale, University of Buea, Cameroon

Members of the Editorial Board:

Prof. Yamb Belle Emmanuel, University of Douala, Cameroon

Ambe J. Njoh, Ph.D., Professor of Environmental Science & Policy, School of Geosciences, University of South Florida, USA

Prof. John Akande, Bowen University, Nigeria

Prof. Talla Pierre Kisito, University of Dschang, Cameroon

Prof. Rosemary Shafack, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Njimanted Godfrey Forgha, University of Bamenda, Cameroon

Prof. Nzalie Joseph, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Mouange Ruben, IUT University of Ngaoundere, Cameroon

Prof. Boum Alexander, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Patrick Wanyu Kongnyuy, University of Bamenda, Cameroon

Prof. Tchuen Ghyslain, IUT Badjoun, University of Dschang, Cameroon

Prof. Rose Frii-Manyi Anjoh, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Foadieng Emmanuel, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Tchinda Rene, IUT Badjoun, University of Dschang, Cameroon

Prof. Tabi Pascal Tabot, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Katte Valentine, University of Bamenda, Cameroon

Prof. Zinkeng Martina, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Obama Belinga Christian Theophile, University of Ebolowa, Cameroon

ISSN 2709-3409 (Online)

Prof. Nkongho Anyi Joseph, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Cordelia Givechek Kometa, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Ngouateu Wouagfack Paiguy, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Tchakoutio Alain, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Morfaw Bertrand, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Tamba Gaston, IUT University, Douala, Cameroon
Prof. Koumi Simon, ENS, Ebolowa, University of Yaounde I
Prof. Ajongakoh Raymond, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Ntabe Eric, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Abanda Henry Fonbiyen, Oxford Brookes University, UK
Dr. Luis Alberto Torrez Cruz, University of Witwatersrand, South Africa
Dr. Aloyem Kaze Claude Vidal, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Mfombep Priscilla Mebong, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Asoba Gillian, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Bahel Benjamin, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Agbortoko Ayuk Nkem, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Mouzong Pemi, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Orock Fidelis Tanyi, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Wanie Clarkson Mvo, University of Bamenda, Cameroon
Dr. Molombe Jeff Mbella, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Emmanuel Tata Sunjo, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Ndi Roland Akoh, University of Yaounde I, Cameroon
Dr. Kinfack Juetsa Aubin, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Kamda Silapeux Aristide, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Roland Ndah Njoh, University of Buea, Cameroon

Table of Contents

NUMERISATION	1
NONLINEAR NUMERICAL APPROXIMATIONS OF TRANSPORT COEFFICIENTS AND PHENOMENOLOGICAL COEFFICIENTS GOVERNING THE COCOA DRYING PROCESS	2
AGRICULTURE	33
IMPACT OF MECHANIZATION ON AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTIVITY IN CAMEROON	34
GEOGRAPHY	48
EVALUATION OF URBAN DEVELOPMENT IN NKONGSAMBA, LITTORAL REGION, CAMEROON: CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS FOR SUSTAINABILITY	49
LE MONT NGAOUNDERE, UN GEOMORPHOSITE D'ESCALADE, PEPITE DU DEVELOPPEMENT DU TOURISME D'OBSERVATION DANS LA VINA ADAMAOUA (CAMEROUN)	74
FOSTERING REGIONAL GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT THROUGH A DECENTRALISED PERSPECTIVE: LESSONS FROM KUMBA AND TIKO MUNICIPALITIES, SOUTH WEST REGION, CAMEROON	94
MANAGEMENT	118
WORKFORCE DIVERSITY: A CONTRIBUTION TO EMPLOYEES' PERFORMANCE IN STATE UNIVERSITIES IN CAMEROON	119
SCIENCE OF EDUCATION	137
THE EFFECT OF AUTOMATIC PROMOTION ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF INTELLECTUAL SKILLS BY FORM ONE STUDENTS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN THE KUMBA II MUNICIPALITY, MEME DIVISION, SOUTH WEST REGION OF CAMEROON	138
LA RESPONSABILITE DES MEMBRES DE LA COMMUNAUTE EDUCATIVE DANS LA PRODUCTION DES VIOLENCES EN MILIEU SCOLAIRE AU CAMEROUN: CAS DES PARENTS D'ELEVES DEVIANTS DES COLLEGES PRIVES CEBER ET IPS A YAOUNDE 4	157
LA DIFFAMATION, LES DÉCLARATIONS MENSONGÈRES, L'OUTRAGE ET LES FAUSSES NOUVELLES DIRIGÉS À L'ENDROIT DES ENSEIGNANTS COMME PRATIQUES SOCIOÉDUCATIVES DÉVIANTES	202
HISTORY	222
TRANSFORMATION OF BAKUNDU-LAND UNDER BRITISH COLONIAL ADMINISTRATION, 1922 - 1960	223

AGRICULTURE

IMPACT OF MECHANIZATION ON AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTIVITY IN CAMEROON

Eric Joel Tchinda Kamdem*¹
Olivier Dimala Dimala²

University Of Douala

* Corresponding author: erictchinda81@yahoo.fr

Submission Date: 14/04/2024

Acceptation Date: 21/06/2024

To cite this article:

Abstract

The aim of this study is to assess the impact of mechanization on agricultural productivity in Cameroon. To achieve this objective, we use Propensity Score Matching techniques on data from the fourth Cameroon Household Survey (CHS IV). The results of the analysis show that farming households using machines on their farms are more productive than their counterparts using traditional farming tools. Indeed, mechanization increases agricultural productivity by 449851 FCFA per monetary unit of input engaged in the agricultural campaign. This effect is statistically significant at the 1% threshold. These results show that mechanization is necessary to improve agricultural yields for Cameroonian farmers. Consequently, we recommend that public authorities improve farmers' level of mechanization by distributing or granting subsidies for the purchase of agricultural machinery.

Keywords: agricultural productivity, mechanization, Propensity Score Matching

1 Introduction

As in most African countries, agriculture in Cameroon plays an important role in the process of reducing poverty and combating food insecurity (Sofack, 2018). It is supposed to provide the rest of the economy with the resources it needs to function. Despite the marginal decline in its share of GDP in recent years, agriculture remains one of the most important sectors in terms of contribution to GDP, accounting for around 20% of GDP (INS¹, 2022). Given Cameroon's potential (great availability in Arab lands, favourable climatic conditions, etc.), development experts believe that the agricultural sector could become the main source of development in Cameroon (Takam-Fongang et al., 2019; Molua, 2016; Temple, 2001). Such a dynamic requires perfect mechanization of the agricultural sector. Mechanization is understood as the use of tools and machines (tractors, harvesters, threshers, etc.) for land reclamation, production and post-harvest techniques (Cossar, 2019). In fact, mechanization is supposed to facilitate and improve the performance of agricultural operations, increase the area under cultivation and enhance the value of human labour freed up for less arduous and/or more productive tasks (Binswanger et al., 1987).

Aware of the role of mechanization as a promoter of agricultural growth, Cameroon, under the aegis of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (MINADER), has set up several programs to encourage the acquisition of modern farming equipment. These include the "Grassfield" Participatory and Decentralized Rural Development Project, the PSSA² and PNVRA³. One of the most recent efforts made by the State is the distribution of SONALIKA tractors of various power ratings (DI 60, DI 75, DI 90) to farmers, in order to improve the level of agricultural mechanization.

The objective of these programs is not only to improve agricultural production through the financing of modern operating equipment (screener⁴, thresher, tarare⁵, and bagger⁶), but also to facilitate the marketing of agricultural products through the financing of a batch of packaged equipment (computer equipment, and motorcycles). Despite this significant number of development projects initiated with a view to reducing major constraints on the adoption of modern farm equipment, we still observe low adoption rates (Ngu-Jiofack et al. 2019; World Bank, 2007). As a result, food production in Cameroon is not in line with population growth. However, access to modern farming equipment should make it possible to improve agricultural production, and therefore to serve an increasing population (Carter and Weibe, 1990; Feder et al. 1990). Thus, to ensure food security in Cameroon, it is necessary to improve the rate of adoption of agricultural technologies by farmers, particularly the use of agricultural machinery, in order to improve the efficiency of agricultural production, create more agricultural surplus economies (Ngu-Jiofack et al., 2020). This excessive enthusiasm in the matter, however, lacks solid scientific evidence to support the preponderant role of mechanization on agricultural yields in Cameroon. Indeed, development theorists have focused more on

¹ National Institute of Statistics

² Special Food Safety Program

³ National Agricultural Extension and Advisory Program

⁴ Device for sorting or sifting seeds or harvest products according to their size

⁵ Agricultural machine used to dust or separate seeds

⁶ Machines that allow the packaging of products, liquids, fluids or solids.

issues of land security, improved variety options and agricultural financing (Tchinda-Kamdem and Kamdem, 2020; Takam-Fongang et al., 2019 ; Niée-Foning et al., 2015; Nyemeck-Binam et al., 2005). Work on agricultural mechanization is rare or even non-existent in the context of Cameroon. In this sense, this study aims to provide scientific lessons on the impact of mechanization on agricultural productivity in Cameroon.

The objective of this article is to analyse the impact of mechanization on agricultural productivity in Cameroon. The remainder of the document is organized as follows. Section 2 presents a brief review of the literature. Section 3 presents the methodology adopted. The results of the model estimation are presented and discussed in Section 4. The last section concludes the paper and presents some economic policy recommendations.

2 Literature review

The effects of agricultural mechanization can be seen in (i) improved land quality; (ii) an increase in the degree of polyculture of the land; (iii) and an increase in the area farmed. Indeed, mechanization enables land preparation (levelling, turning, scarification, etc.), which can improve land quality better than standard farming methods (manual farming methods, animal traction) (Zhou et al., 2019; Peng and Zhang, 2020; Aslan et al., 2007).

Irrigation, drainage and mechanical spraying can effectively mitigate the risks that typically affect agricultural campaigns (drought, flooding, insect pests, weeds, etc.). These practices coupled with mechanical seeding can make crop distribution more uniform and promote growth (Berdnikova, 2018; Hu and Zhang, 2018). In this way, agricultural mechanization increases the degree of polyculture of land compared with conventional farming techniques (Qu et al., 2021). Finally, by saving labour, mechanization also increases the area of land farmed. The larger the area farmers farm, the higher the production frontier, and the greater the role agriculture plays in increasing agricultural output and income (Chen, 2015). Empirical evidence based on these theoretical precepts can be found in the economic literature. Indeed, it has been demonstrated in the Asian context that agricultural mechanization is one of the means of increasing the level of green agricultural development and producing high-quality products (Xu and Song, 2021; Liu et al., 2021; Mottaleb, Roller et al., 2016; Chen and Zhang, 2021). On the other hand, many development theorists argue that the use of agricultural mechanization by farmers has been considered the spindle of the agricultural revolt in sub-Saharan Africa, and has contributed significantly to increased production of food crops and other agricultural products (Kirui, 2019; Benin, 2015; Ayandiji and Olofinsao, 2015; Pingali, 2007).

3 Methodology

The achievement of our objectives is based on the application of the "Propensity score matching (PSM)" method. Using non-experimental data, this approach produces a control group (non-beneficiaries) that is as similar as possible to the treatment group (program beneficiaries). The impact of the program is then estimated, given that the samples of beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries have the same characteristics. On this basis, the difference in outcome variables is attributed to the program's impact. In our case, in our case, we compared the agricultural productivity differential induced by agricultural mechanization (i.e. the use of machines in the cultivation process) and the

manual use of traditional tools in cultivation. In other words, the aim is to analyse whether or not mechanization improves agricultural productivity. Our methodology consists in presenting the principle of PSM and the analysis method.

3.1 Propensity score matching principle

The general idea behind this analysis method is to determine or construct a statistical comparison group based on the probability of participating in the program. (Rosembaum and Rubin, 1983): $P(X) = pr(D = 1/x)$. Let's consider a situation where we need to assess the impact of a particular treatment on an individual's health. "D" represents a binary variable which takes the value 1 if the individual receives the treatment and 0 if not. "Y" represents the variable on which the treatment is supposed to act. "Y0" captures the state of individuals before the treatment is administered, and "Y1" reflects their state after they have been treated. The average treatment effect is expressed as follows: $\Delta\bar{Y} = E(Y_1 - Y_0 / D = 1)$ (1)

The breakdown gives: $\Delta\bar{Y} = E(Y_1 / D = 1) - E(Y_0 / D = 1)$ (2)

The second term ($E(Y_0 / D = 1)$) on the right represents the counterfactual sample or comparison group, and describes the state of treated individuals before they receive the treatment. In the medical sciences, it is sometimes possible to observe the situation of patients before the application of the treatment, in which case we have a pure comparison group. On the other hand, it is more complex to have a control group when we are interested in the effect of a transfer or social program on the well-being of individuals. This is because, for the most part, household surveys provide a snapshot of the situation of households at one point in time (cross-section), and therefore do not allow us to observe the situation of households receiving aid before they receive it. In other words, the component $E(Y_0 / D = 1)$ is unobserved.

3.2 Analysis method

This section describes the steps involved in estimating PSM, and the variables and data used in the analysis.

3.2.1 Steps in estimating PSM

PSM is estimated in three stages: propensity score estimation, determination of common support and estimation of standard deviations.

3.2.1.1 Propensity score estimation

This estimate is made using a logit or probit model, which calculates the probability of participating in the program (farm mechanization or not). Once the propensity scores have been determined, the treated cases are associated with the untreated cases closest in terms of propensity scores (and therefore observable characteristics). Once the propensity scores have been estimated for each individual in the sample, we determine the common support to ensure that for each individual who has mechanized his or her farming, we can find at least one individual who has not mechanized his or her farming, but who has the same propensity scores as the latter.

3.2.1.2 Determining the common substrate

Two main techniques can be used to construct the common support. The Kernel technique and the nearest-neighbour matching technique. In the first technique, each farmer participating in the program is matched with the whole sample of the comparison group. However, for each observation in the treatment group, we observe what is the average generalized observation weight in the control group. These weights are inversely proportional to the distance between each observation group and the control group, based on the "propensity score" distribution. In the second technique, each treated observation is matched with the mean of five nearest neighbours from the comparison sample, again based on the "propensity score" distribution. To ensure comparability between the treatment and comparison groups, the sample is restricted to the region of common support defined by the standard deviation values of the "propensity scores", in which observations between the treatment and control groups can be sought.

3.2.1.3 Standard deviation estimation

The standard deviation estimate is obtained by applying the bootstrap method, which consists in replicating the entire estimate on a random sample with the same discount as the initial sample, and determining the standard deviation of the entire distribution of the estimators obtained. This standard deviation estimate takes into account the fact that the propensity scores have been estimated. As a result, each bootstrap must take into account not only the association of the random sample, but also the estimation of the scores.

3.3 Description of data and variables to be used

3.3.1 Variables used

Drawing on Benin (2015), we built a binary variable to capture agricultural mechanization. This variable is worth 1 if the farmer uses, among other things, motor pumps, tractors and threshers, and 0 if the farmer uses traditional tools such as the hoe or machete to plow the fields. Agricultural productivity is captured through the ratio of total production in monetary value to all factors taken into account in the production process.

$$\text{total productivity} = \frac{\text{quantity produced in monetary value}}{\sum_{i=1}^n X_i}$$

Where X_i represents the quantity of input i used in the production process.

The variables used in this study are summarized in the following table:

Table 1: variables used in the analysis

1.3.2 Data description

Variables	Nature of variables	Variable description
Mechanization	Dummy	1 if the farmer uses machinery on the farm and 0 if he uses traditional production tools (hoe, machete, etc.).
Agricultural productivity	Digital and continuous	Ratio between total production in thousands of FCFA and all production factors taken into account in production.
gender	Dummy	1 if the farmer is a man and 0 if he is a woman
Age	Digital and continuous	Age of sex of head of household
Education level	Dummy	1 if the farmer is instructed and 0 otherwise
Household size	Digital and continuous	Number of persons in household
Credit	Dummy	1 if the farmer has access to credit and 0 otherwise
Farm size	categorical variable	It takes the value 1 if the farmer farms land with an area between $0 \leq \text{terre} < 4$ hectares; 2 if the area is between $5 \leq \text{terre} < 100$ hectares and 3 if the land area is > 100 hectares.
Labor force	Digital and continuous	Total number of people usually working on the farm

To achieve our objective, we used the data from the fourth Cameroon Household Survey (CHS IV). These data were collected in 2014 by the government through the National Institute of Statistics (NIS). The main objective of this survey is to update the poverty profile, but also to take stock of the evolution of indicators measuring household living conditions established in 2007. The aim of building this database is to facilitate comparative analysis between households. The geographic scope of the survey is the national territory. The operation concerns all ordinary households residing on the entire national territory, excluding members of the diplomatic corps and their households. The statistical unit is the household, defined as a set of one or more persons (socio-economic unit), whether or not related by blood or marriage, living in one or more dwellings in the same concession, pooling their resources to meet day-to-day expenses, usually eating meals together, and recognizing the authority of a single person as head of household (or reference person). The units of observation are both the household (housing, habitat, indivisible household expenditure, etc.) and the individuals (demographic characteristics, individual expenditure, etc.). The information gathered in this survey covers all 10 regions of Cameroon. The cities of Douala and Yaoundé constitute two separate strata. The ten regions are organized around three strata: urban, semi-urban and rural. The survey covers 37 strata, including 15 rural and semi-urban, 12 urban and 10 in the Yaoundé and Douala strata. The sample comprises 13,000 households in 1,024 survey zones (ZD). This sample includes some 268 households in 20 DZs that were the subject of the pilot survey coupled with the light survey in March-April 2014. The multitude of indicators offered by this database seems appropriate for assessing the impact of

ISSN 2709-3409 (Online)

mechanization on agricultural productivity. It should be remembered that this study focuses on rural farming households. In fact, our sample size is 2130 farm households.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics for the variables used

Variables	Observation	Mean	Std-dv	Minimum	Maximum	
Farm mechanization	2130	0,3196991	0,4664696	0	1	
Agricultural productivity	2130	80600,44	1101220	2.00e-06	5.00e+07	
Gender	2130	0,493653	0,500077	0	1	
Age	2130	25,87776	20,54289	1	95	
Education level	2130	0,6793606	0,4668321	0	1	
Household size	2130	5,432064	3,479812	1	27	
Credit	2130	0,0437236	0,2045274	0	1	
Farm size	Small farm	2130	0,7884344	0,4085144	0	1
	Medium farm	2130	0,1560884	0,3630245	0	1
	Large farm	2130	0,0554772	0,2289632	0	1
Labor force	2130	3,648801	5,744671	0	222	

As presented, Table 2 does not provide sufficient information on the characteristics of households according to whether or not they mechanize farming. It is for this reason that we present in the following Table 3 the descriptive statistics of households according to whether or not they have mechanized cultivated areas.

Table 3: farmers' characteristics

Variables	Agricultural mechanization		Traditional farming tools		
	Observation	Mean	Observation	Mean	
Agricultural productivity	682	449856,1	1448	4,282928	
Gender	682	0,513196	1448	0,515884	
Age	682	25,87977	1448	28,47652	
Education level	682	0,7258065	1448	0,6574586	
Household size	682	5,521994	1448	5,671961	
Credit	682	0,0557185	1448	0,0379834	
Farm size	Small farm	682	0,7346041	1448	0,7914365
	Medium farm	682	0,1979472	1448	0,1546961
	Large farm	682	0,0674487	1448	0,0538674
Labor force	682	4,265396	1448	3,586326	

Exploring this table, we note that for the same variables, farmers using machines and those using traditional tools for cultivation have different characteristics. To assess the impact of mechanization on agricultural productivity, it is necessary to neutralize these differences, so that the effect obtained from the estimation is the sole consequence of crop mechanization and not of the specific characteristics of the farmers involved. This is why, in the following subsection, we use Matching techniques. These techniques will reduce the differences between individuals so that the observed result is solely the consequence of crop mechanization and not the result of farmers' characteristics. The challenge here is to reduce as far as possible the biases associated with the observable characteristics of the two sub-groups.

4 Results and discussion

4.1 Estimation of propensity scores using probit regression

Table 4: Probit modelling of factors explaining mechanization

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>P-value</i>	
<i>Gender</i>	-0,034622	0,547	
<i>Age</i>	-0,0045533	0,001	
<i>Education level</i>	0,1777214	0,004	
<i>Household size</i>	-0,0193629	0,034	
<i>Credit</i>	0,1870394	0,171	
<i>Farm size</i>	<i>Medium farm</i>	0,2238114	0,004
	<i>Large farm</i>	0,1574582	0,197
<i>Labor force</i>	0,0065485	0,291	
<i>Constance</i>	-0,4221432	0,000	

***1% significance, **5% significance, *10% significance

The modelling results show that farmer age, level of education, household size and farm size significantly influence farm mechanization. Thus, older and better-educated farmers are more likely to mechanize cultivation. Similarly, the analysis shows that, compared with small farmers, medium-sized farmers (i.e. those with holdings of between 5 and 100 hectares) are more inclined to mechanize farming. This result is not surprising, as many development theorists have demonstrated in the Asian context that mechanization is an indispensable measure for irrigating, draining, spraying and ploughing large areas (Ji et al. 2021; Peng and Zhang, 2020). In fact, the use of machinery in cultivation would facilitate land preparation, particularly for large areas. The previous table also reveals that household size has a negative influence on farm mechanization. In other words, the larger the household, the less farmers resort to mechanized farming. We believe this is

due to the fact that the people present in the household are labour substitutes. In fact, they all participate in all the cultivation activities involved in the production process. The available family labour thus helps to amortize the need for additional labour, which is generally covered by machinery. This is generally true for small farms and where there is no rural exodus.

4.2 Matching quality tests

Before presenting the results, it is important to ensure that the quality of the propensity scores is good. To assess this, it is necessary to check the balancing property. The basic idea here is to compare the difference between the treatment and control groups after and before matching, and check whether this difference remains. If there are several differences between the characteristics of the two groups, this implies that the matching has not been completely successful, and should therefore be improved. Before matching, we saw that there were differences between the characteristics of farmers who use machines and those who do not. After matching, it was found that there is only one significant difference in terms of mean between the two groups. This difference concerns the labour variable (Table 5). Our two groups are now comparable on one variable: labour. We can validate the hypothesis of a good match, since only one of the 7 variables is significantly different from zero.

Table 5 : Matching test

Sample matched by 5 nearest neighbors

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Unmatched sample</i>			<i>Kernel-matched sample</i>						
	<i>Mean</i>		<i>P-value</i>	<i>Mean</i>		<i>P-value</i>	<i>Mean</i>		<i>P-value</i>	
	<i>Treatment</i>	<i>Control</i>		<i>Treatment</i>	<i>Control</i>		<i>Treatment</i>	<i>Control</i>		
<i>Gender</i>	0, 5132	0, 51588	0,908	0, 5132	0, 51049	0,920	0, 5132	0, 51049	0,920	
<i>Age</i>	25,88	28,477	0,010	25,88	25,341	0,621	25,88	0, 25.341	0,621	
<i>Education level</i>	0, 72581	0, 65746	0,002	0, 72581	0, 73245	0,783	0, 72581	0, 73245	0,783	
<i>Household size</i>	5,522	5,672	0,377	5,522	5,5349	0,948	5,522	5,5349	0,948	
<i>Credit</i>	0, 05572	0, 03798	0,062	0,05572	0, 045	0,366	0, 05572	0, 045	0,366	
<i>Farm size</i>	<i>Medium farm</i>	0, 19795	0, 1547	0,013	0, 19795	0, 18384	0,508	0, 19795	0, 18384	0,508
	<i>Large farm</i>	0, 06745	0, 05387	0,212	0, 06745	0,06134	0,646	0, 06745	0, 06134	0,646
	<i>Labor force</i>	4,2654	3.5863	0,033	4,2654	3,3752	0,033	4,2654	3,3752	0,000

4.3 Average effect of mechanization on agricultural productivity

The indicator of the impact of mechanization on agricultural productivity is yield per monetary unit. The impact of mechanization on yield per monetary unit indicates whether the output of households using machines is higher than that of households using traditional tools. The following table shows the results of the estimation of the average effects of mechanization on agricultural productivity. To ensure the robustness of the mean effects estimate, we first calculated the differences in the outcome variable between the treatment group and the comparison group. Then, to obtain the standard deviation, we ran 100 replications using the Bootstrap command in Stata 17.

Table 6: Average effect of mechanization on agricultural productivity

	Kernel			5 nearest neighbors		
	ATT	Std-dv	P> z	ATT	Std-dv	P> z
Agricultural productivity	449851,8	134791,8	0,001	449852,1	134791,8	0,001
Observation	2130					

***significant at 1%, significant at 5%, significant at 10%, with z the student statistic

The results of the mean effects estimation for both methods (Kernel matching and nearest-five-neighbor matching) show that farmers who mechanize their crop increase their yield per monetary unit by around 449851 FCFA. We find here the effect we might expect, and which is widely shared in the literature, namely: mechanization increases agricultural productivity (Chen and Zhang, 2021; Xu and Song, 2021; Kirui, 2019; Ayandiji and Olofinsao, 2015; Benin, 2015). This effect is statistically significant at the 1% threshold. The hypothesis that mechanization improves agricultural productivity is therefore verified in the Cameroon context.

5 Conclusion

The aim of this paper was to assess the impact of mechanization on agricultural productivity in Cameroon. Econometric results showed that farm households using machinery on their plantation are more productive than farm households using traditional production tools on their plantation. We therefore recommend that public authorities improve the level of agricultural mechanization among farmers. In addition, the State must resolve the constraints that farmers face on an ongoing basis. These include

the lack of adequate training for machine operators, the scarcity of spare parts, and the poor quality of machinery.

6 References

- Ayandiji, A, and O. T Olofinsao,. 2015. "Socio-Economic Factors Affecting Adoption of Farm Mechanization by Cassava Farmers in Ondo State Nigeria." *Ers in Ondo State, Nigeria. IOSR J. Env. Sci. Tox. Foo. Tech* 9 (3): 39–45.
- Benin, S. 2015. "Impact of Ghana's Agricultural Mechanization Services Center Program." *Agricultural Economics* 46: 103–17.
- Binswanger, H, G Donovan, and R Fabre,. 1987. *Agricultural Mechanization: Issues and Options*. World Bank.
- Carter, M.R, and K.D Weibe,. 1990. "Access to Capital and Its Impact on Agrarian Structure and Productivity in Kenya." *American Journal of Agricultural Economics* 70 (5): 1146–50. <https://doi.org/doi.org/10.2307/1242523>.
- Chen, S. S, and X. Q Zhang,. 2021. "Agriculture Green and High-Quality Development of Fujian Province under New Era." *Sci. Tech. Mana. Res* 18: 96–104.
- Cossar, F. 2019. "Impact of Mechanization on Smallholder Agricultural Production: Evidence from Ghana." In *Contributed Paper Prepared for Presentation at the 93rd Annual Conference of the Agricultural Economics Society*. University of Warwick, England.
- Feder, G, J.Y Lau, Y Lin, and L Xiaopeng,. 1990. "The Relationship between Credit and Productivity in Chinese Agriculture: A Microeconomic Model of Disequilibrium." *American Journal of Agricultural Economics* 72 (5): 1151–57. <https://doi.org/doi:10.2307/1242524>.
- Ji, Z. X, X.L Wang, L Li, X. K Guan, and Y. Q Xu,. 2021. "The Evolution of Cultivated Land Utilization Efficiency and Its Influencing Factors in Nanyang Basin." *J. Nat. Resour* 36: 688–701.
- Kirui, O. 2019. "The Agricultural Mechanization in Africa: Micro-Level Analysis of State Drivers and Effects." *ZEF-Discussion Papers on Development Policy*, no. 272.
- Liu, T, Y. Z Cui, and J. J Huo,. 2021. "Research on Allocation Efficiency Measurement and Spatial Agglomeration Effect of Agricultural Machinery Equipment under High-Quality Development Background." *J. Chin. Agric. Mechan* 5: 123–28.
- Molua, E, L. 2016. "The Economic Impact of Climate Change on Agriculture in Cameroon." *World Bank Policy Research Working Paper*, no. 4364.
- Mottaleb, K. A, R. S Roller, and O Erenstein,. 2016. "Factors Associated with Small-Scale Agricultural Machinery Adoption in Bangladesh: Census Findings." *J. Rur. Stu* 46: 155–68.
- Ngu-Jiofack, L, Ibrahima-Saidou, O Mefeng, and R Njueze,. 2019. "Analysis of the Hardware and Software Weaknesses of Mechanical Tool Technology in Agricultural Mechanization: Case of SONALIKA Brand Tractors in Cameroon." *International Journal for Research in Applied Science & Engineering Technology (IJRASET)* 7.

- Ngu-Jiofack, L, O Mefeng, and Ibrahima-Saidou. 2020. "Insight into Agricultural Mechanization in Cameroon: Case of Farm Operators, Users of Agricultural Equipment and Machines." *International Journal of Engineering Research & Science (IJOER)* 6.
- Niée-Foning, M, J. J Ambagna, and Fondo-Sikod,. 2015. "L'incidence de La Sécurité Foncière Sur La Productivité Des Ménages Agricoles Camerounais." Available at: <https://www.sfer.asso.fr/source/jrсс2014/jrсс-2014-Niее-Foning.pdf>.
- Nyemeck-Binam, J, J Tonye, and Njankoua-Wandji,. 2005. "Source of Technical Efficiency among Small Holder Maize and Peanut Farmers in the Slash and Burn Agriculture Zone of Cameroon." *Journal of Economic Cooperation* 26 (1): 193-210.
- Peng, C, and C Zhang,. 2020. "Assessment of Agricultural Mechanization on Farmers' Grain Aggregated Production Efficiency." *J. South. China Agric. Univ* 19: 93-102.
- Pingali, P. 2007. "Chapter 54 Agricultural Mechanization: Adoption Patterns and Economic Impact." *Handbook of Agricultural Economics* 3: 2779-2805.
- Rosenbaum, P. R., Rubin, D. B. 1983. "The Central Role of the Propensity Score in Observational Studies for Causal Effects." *Biometrika*, 41-55.
- Sofack, N. 2018. *Nouvelle Géopolitique de L'agriculture et de L'alimentation : Quelles Politiques Publiques de Sécurité Alimentaire Au Cameroun ?*. L'Harmattan.
- Takam-Fongang, G. M, C. B Kamdem, and G. Q Kane,. 2019. "Adoption and Impact of Improved Maize Varieties on Maize Yields: Evidence from Central Cameroon." *Review of Development Economics* 23 (1): 172-88.
- Tchinda-Kamdem, E. J, and C. B Kamdem,. 2020. "Land Tenure Security, Credit Access and Agricultural Productivity in Cameroon." *AERC Research Paper* 395.
- Temple, L. 2001. "Quantification Des Productions et Des Échanges de Fruits et Légumes Au Cameroun." *Cahiers Agricultures* 10 (2): 87-94.
- World Bank,. 2007. "World Development Report 2008: Agriculture for Development." *World Bank Publications, Washington DC*.
- Xu, D, and W Song,. 2021. "Research on the Evaluation of Green Development of Agriculture in the Perspective of Rural Revitalization." *Study Explo* 3: 130-36.

Appendices

